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Generation Z's Human-Artificial Intelligence Collaborative Capabilities: The Application of Social Learning Theory (SLT)

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Abstract

The potential for artificial intelligence (AI) to surpass human intelligence remains debatable, yet its role as an enabling technology for economic growth and societal empowerment is undeniable. This research investigates the dynamic interplay between Generation Z and AI within collaborative contexts, focusing on the factors that enhance human-AI partnerships. Leveraging Social Learning Theory, the study explores how observation, imitation, and reinforcement shape Generation Z's interactions with AI tools and systems. AI learning motivation, personality traits, AI collaborative learning and AI Self-Efficiency are also examined.

AI encompasses diverse technologies, including machine learning, deep learning, and symbolic AI, enabling machines to perceive, learn, and make decisions akin to human cognition. Since its conceptualization in the 1950s, AI research has addressed societal and business challenges, advancing theories on its adoption for crisis management, economic equality, and organizational performance. Scholars emphasize that humans augmented by AI outperform those without, underscoring the necessity of collaboration between AI and human intelligence to tackle complex problems and enhance skills.

The findings aim to guide responsible AI integration by emphasizing explainable AI, transparency, and ethical governance. By exploring Generation Z's unique engagement with AI, this research proposes new directions for enhancing collaborative capabilities and fostering innovative, ethical applications across sectors.

Keywords: Generation Z, Human-Artificial Intelligence, Collaborative Capabilities, Social Learning Theory

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